

**A SCOPING REVIEW ON COMMUNITY-BASED
INTERVENTION PROGRAMS FOR OPTIMISING BRAIN
HEALTH DETERMINANTS ACROSS THE LIFE COURSE IN
AFRICA (2015-2025)**

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Figure 1: The PRISMA flow of the selection process

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LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

ABDRN	African Brain Disorders Research Network
AMARI	African Mental Health Research Initiative
APCDR	African Partnership for Chronic Disease Research
ASQ	Ages and Stages Questionnaire
BOT	Bruininks-Oseretsky Test
BSID-III ST	Bayley Scales of Infant Development III Screening Test
CNS	Central Nervous System
DCHS	Drakenstein Child Health Study
HAALSI	Health and Aging in Africa Longitudinal Studies
HIV	Human Immunodeficiency Virus
KABC	Kaufman Assessment Battery for Children
MDAT	Malawi Development Assessment Tool
MSEL	Mullen Scales of Early Learning
PICO	Problem, Intervention, Comparison, and Outcome
PRISMA	Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses
RCPM	Raven's Color Progressive Matrices
RSPM	Raven's Standard Progressive Matrices
SAM	Severe Acute Malnutrition
SDOH	Social Determinants of Health
TOVA	Tests of Variables of Attention
WHO	World Health Organisation

ABSTRACT

Background: Brain health comprises optimal functioning of the brain across cognitive, emotional, sensory, behavioural and motor domains. The brain health domain is increasingly being recognised as a public health priority, shaped by social determinants and life-course exposures. In Africa, limited research and intervention frameworks have constrained efforts to address the growing burden of neurological and cognitive health conditions. This scoping review aims to investigate the breadth of community-based interventions and programs implemented in Africa (2020–2025) that align with the World Health Organization’s five determinant clusters of brain health that include: physical health, healthy environments, safety and security, learning and social connection, and access to quality services, across the life course.

Methods: Guided by the PRISMA framework, systematic searches were conducted in PubMed, Scopus, Science Direct, and Web of Science. Eligible studies included quantitative, qualitative, or mixed-methods research reporting on community-based or community-based interventions targeting brain health outcomes in African populations. Data were extracted on study design, population, intervention type, determinant category, and outcomes.

Results: 31 studies were used in this review. Few studies explicitly developed community-led brain health interventions, with only two programs (a home visiting model and a psychosocial stimulation program) identified. The majority of studies focused on physical health determinants entries ($n = 19$, 61%), especially maternal and child health, where nutrition, early stimulation, and breastfeeding support were linked to improved neurodevelopmental outcomes. Longitudinal studies provided further insight into ageing, social determinants, and cognitive decline, with pension access emerging as a protective factor. However, limited evidence was found on interventions targeting healthy environments, financial security, or access to specialised services. Tools used to measure outcomes were primarily adapted from international cognitive assessments, underscoring challenges in contextualising measures for African populations.

Conclusion: Community-based strategies hold significant potential for advancing brain health in Africa but remain underdeveloped and unevenly distributed across the life course. Existing evidence underscores the importance of maternal and child health interventions, while highlighting gaps in the health of adults and older populations.

DECLARATION

The results presented in this dissertation are based on my research in the Faculty of Health,
Liverpool John Moores University.

All assistance received from other individuals and organisations has been acknowledged and
full reference is made to all published and unpublished sources used.

This dissertation has not been previously submitted for a degree at any other institution.

Signed: _____ Date: 21ST /SEP/2025

BACKGROUND INFORMATION

Brain health has emerged as a critical pillar of overall well-being, influencing cognitive, emotional, sensory, behavioural, and motor functioning across the life course (“Brain health,” n.d.). Once framed mainly within the context of mental illness, brain health is now recognized as a distinct yet interconnected dimension of health that warrants targeted research, policy attention, and practice. Brain health refers to the optimal functioning of the brain across cognitive, emotional, sensory, behavioural, and motor domains (*Optimizing Brain Health Across the Life Course*, 2022). Maintaining optimal brain health has become a key public health priority, as the widespread impact of social determinants of health is increasingly recognised, contributing to disparities in brain health. (Bach et al., 2024).

The challenge of advancing brain research in Africa has been increasing recently, with more studies gaining momentum on the continent (Aborode et al., n.d.). Most of the time, these kinds of studies have happened in the West, creating a disproportionate gap in the literature on the brain health of the African population. However, we have seen the rise of institutions like African Brain Disorders Research Network (ABDRN), the African Mental Health Research Initiative (AMARI) and African Partnership for Chronic Disease Research (APCDR), which have led important initiatives in exploring Africa's determinants and burdens of chronic disease, increasingly tackling matters of the brain (Aborode et al., n.d.).

Brain Health Disease Burden

Over the years, brain health has evolved into a multifaceted concept, encompassing various brain and central nervous system (CNS) conditions, collectively referred to as neurological conditions. Similar to mental health burden, neurological conditions have been shown to have a significant disease burden globally. Neurological conditions such as stroke, dementia, and migraine are among the leading causes of poor health worldwide, affecting over 40% of the global population in 2021 (“Global, regional, and national burden of disorders affecting the

nervous system, 1990–2021,” 2024). This burden has been felt differently across Low-Middle Income Countries (LMICs), with Africa contributing to many of these countries (“World Bank Open Data,” n.d.).

Similarly, there has been a shortage of experts, such as neurologists and neurosurgeons, to help manage brain health conditions. This further highlights the growing gap in advancing brain health equity. (Bach et al., 2024). Across the African continent, the presence of trained neurologists is far below the global average, with a ratio of 0.03 neurologists per 100,000 people, in stark contrast to Europe's 8.45 neurologists per 100,000 individuals (Klein et al., 2023)

Some of the most significant deficits have been in child neurology specialists and access to training, which were evident in countries classified as low-income countries by the World Bank (ranging from 0 to 0.008 child neurologists per 100,000 population). This is further made worse, with data showing that close to seventy-three percent of low-income countries (in Africa and Southeast Asia) lack access to child neurologists (Wilmschurst et al., 2023)

Following this challenge, different brain health intervention strategies have been developed to help lessen the disease burden.

Brain Health Determinants

In 2022, the WHO released a position paper outlining five key determinants of brain health: physical health, healthy environments, safety and security, learning and social connection, and access to quality services (*Optimising Brain Health Across the Life Course*, 2022). These determinants highlight the importance of promotion and prevention efforts that can decrease the incidence of disorders affecting the CNS. The paper emphasises how optimising brain health throughout the lifespan will be essential for improving brain structure and function

across all domains, including cognitive, motor and sensory domains, social-emotional and behavioural areas (*Optimising Brain Health Across the Life Course*, 2022).

To better understand how these determinants contribute to brain health, a comprehensive breakdown is presented, starting with physical health determinants. Physical health's impact on brain health is highlighted early on, from maternal health and the intrauterine cavity. The importance of genetics interplay, food and nutrition is also classified under physical factors to affect brain health. Infections have also been identified to harm the brain directly, with conditions causing meningitis, encephalitis, enterovirus, Human Immunodeficiency Virus (HIV), neurocysticercosis and malaria being highlighted as key factors driving poor brain health. In addition, non-communicable diseases have also been rising, leading to conditions such as stroke, dementia and Parkinson's. The paper advocates for interventions aimed at improving physical health, such as enhancing sleep quality, engaging in regular physical activity, and reducing substance use, which can also positively affect brain development and overall brain health.

Health environments determinants focus on factors within an individual's surroundings that may impact brain health. These factors stretch beyond the mainstream public health concerns to assess how entities such as exposure to heavy metals, harmful pesticides, poorly disposed industrial solvents, continuous air pollution and natural and man-made disasters can influence brain health.

Under the safety and security determinants, the paper approaches the two as physical safety and financial security. Physical security captures how exposure to violence can be detrimental to brain health, while financial security highlights the risk of poverty leading to stress due to financial concerns. This calls for interventions around extreme events, such as humanitarian crises, whose origins and duration can have long-lasting implications for one's brain health.

The importance of learning and social connection was also discussed as essential opportunities for early cognitive development, as well as social and emotional learning experiences that are crucial for brain development in infancy and early childhood. On the other end of the life-course, the availability of social activities and engagement in older adults has been seen to be the most consistent components of social connections for improving cognitive health among individuals with or at risk for Alzheimer's disease (Joshi et al., 2024).

To manage the numerous risk factors that arise, populations need access to quality services that improve brain health. This involves readily accessible, people-centred and responsive services that meet a person's unique needs. Brain health requires specialised access to healthcare personnel, including neurologists, psychiatrists, speech therapists, and many more. These crucial service needs are largely unmet and require strengthening, particularly at the primary care and community levels. Access to diagnostic services such as neuroimaging or electroencephalography is an essential tool for optimising brain health as it allows for early and rapid detection of pathologies, disorders and risk factors.

However, there is limited understanding of how such interventions are designed and implemented to promote brain health within the African community context. Although each determinant is explored in detail and its implications for brain health are discussed, there is no clear framework for how such an approach to interventions should be adopted. This scoping review aims to map existing literature on community-based interventions in Africa that seek to enhance brain health at various life stages, based on the five areas of brain health determinants.

In this review, approaching brain health conditions through the life course, rather than a point incidence, is considered. This approach enables us to view brain health conditions from a broader perspective, one that extends beyond clinical considerations, and adopt a public

health approach. Approaching brain health from a social determinant of health perspective provides an opportunity to help lessen disease burden through community-based interventions, especially in resource-limited areas where access to specialized services might be costly.

Brain Health Across the Life Course

Brain health is shaped by multiple determinants that act and interact across the life course, from prenatal development to older age (Bach et al., 2024). Evidence demonstrates that exposures during sensitive periods, such as pregnancy, early childhood, and later adulthood, can have lasting effects on brain function and resilience (Bach et al., 2024; *Optimizing Brain Health Across the Life Course*, 2022). Understanding how these determinants affect the different stages of the life course is critical to identifying opportunities for intervention and making brain health a priority (Kolappa et al., 2022).

Prenatal and Early Life.

During the early stages of life, maternal health, nutrition, and environmental exposures during pregnancy play a decisive role in shaping brain development. Conditions in which women are born, nurtured and seek their livelihoods before and during pregnancy influence fetal neurodevelopment, with factors such as maternal malnutrition, anaemia, infections, and exposure to toxins linked to adverse cognitive and behavioural outcomes (Patel et al., 2018; Bach et al., 2024). For instance, inadequate access to antenatal care and micronutrient supplementation has been associated with higher risks of developmental delays in infants. These disparities are particularly pronounced in low- and middle-income countries, including many African settings where access to maternal healthcare remains uneven (“The State of the World’s Children 2021 | UNICEF,” 2021).

Childhood and Adolescence.

Early childhood is a critical stage characterised by rapid brain growth and stimulation. Activities such as education are influential during this period. Providing high-quality feeding programs and early childhood education initiatives protects cognitive development and lays the foundation for lifelong brain health (Grantham-McGregor et al., 2007). Conversely, exposure to environmental pollutants like lead, mercury, and air pollution can harm neurocognitive development and academic success (Calderón-Garcidueñas et al., 2015). Adolescence introduces additional determinants, including peer and family environments, substance use and access to safe recreational and educational opportunities (Sawyer et al., 2012).

Adulthood.

Brain health in adulthood is necessary to ensure successful social and economic growth. This is shaped by lifestyle and social determinants, including job security or status, income, the social status of individuals and access to healthcare (Olowoyo et al., 2024). Cardiovascular health is especially relevant, as hypertension, diabetes, and obesity are strongly associated with midlife cognitive decline (Livingston et al., 2020). Adults are susceptible to work-related stress and exposure to occupational hazards, such as neurotoxic chemicals, which further compound risks in many African settings where regulatory frameworks are limited.

Older Age.

In later life, access to social programs and community support plays a crucial role in reducing the risks of cognitive decline and dementia. Pension scheme disparities exist, with African countries having differences compared to their counterparts in regions like South America (Mostert et al., 2025a). In addition, there is limited access to geriatric care, and social isolation increases vulnerability among older adults (“The time to ensure a healthy and dignified ageing for Africans is now | WHO | Regional Office for Africa,” 2025). Evidence

shows that socially engaged older adults, with access to preventive healthcare and community resources, maintain better cognitive functioning compared to their peers without such supports (Wang et al., 2024).

Community-Based Approaches.

Community-based interventions have gained traction as viable strategies for addressing the determinants of brain health in resource-limited settings. Examples include maternal nutrition initiatives, school feeding programs, and community-based care for the elderly (Sadarangani et al., 2020). However, there remains a limited understanding of how such interventions are conceptualised and evaluated across brain health domains, particularly in African contexts (Aborode et al., 2023). A more transparent framework for aligning community-based strategies with determinants across the life course is essential to inform coherent, inclusive, and context-sensitive approaches to brain health promotion. In this case, community-based interventions were those that operated at both the individual and community levels, utilizing resources within the community and beyond the hospital or clinical setting as part of the intervention to mediate brain health outcomes.

OBJECTIVES

The goal of this scoping review was to map African evidence on community-based strategies for optimising brain health across the life course. Specifically, map recent African literature (2020–2025) that examines community-based interventions aligned with the WHO's five determinant clusters of brain health: physical health (e.g., nutrition, exercise), healthy environments (e.g., pollution reduction), safety and security, learning and social connection (e.g., education, social programs), and access to quality services. The study aimed

- To identify the types of community-based research and interventions around brain health determinants for the African context.

- To identify the adoption of the community-based interventions across the life course and the tools used
- To examine the evidence collected and presented on outcomes and effectiveness.

In doing so, this review highlights how African contexts are addressing risks of brain health deterioration through the lens of brain health determinants across the life course.

METHODS

The methods for this scoping review were informed by the six-step procedure outlined by Daudt, van Mossel, and Scott (Daudt et al., 2013) and reported following the PRISMA statement extension for scoping reviews (Tricco et al., 2018)

To transform our topic into searchable queries consistent with databases in accordance with the PICO (Problem, Intervention, Comparison, and Outcome) structure (Petersen et al., 2015). The first category of research questions was broken down and defined the keywords that would be looked for. Our search focused on community-based programs, neurological research and brain health across the life course. 'The life course' was defined as anywhere from intrauterine to late adulthood. Thereafter, the focus was on concepts that included brain health, cognitive health, brain development, and neurodevelopment, captured by terms like "Brain Health," "Cognitive Function," "Neurodevelopment," "Child Development," "Infant Development," "Cognitive Health," "Brain Development," "Brain Function," and "Neurodevelopment."

Intervention: The review targeted community-based programs or community-developed interventions, non-clinical interventions or factors that promote brain health through the five WHO-defined determinant clusters: physical health (e.g., nutrition, exercise), healthy environments (e.g., pollution reduction), safety and security, learning and social connection (e.g., education, social support), and access to quality services (e.g., healthcare access). These are represented by terms such as "Physical Fitness," "Exercise," "Diet," "Nutrition," "Environment," "Social Environment," "Safety," "Social Support," "Education," "Health Services Accessibility," and synonyms like "physical activity," "healthy environment*," "safety," "social connection*," and "access to health services." Intervention and prevention programs are any services, strategies or techniques offered by professionals, paraprofessionals, or laypersons that aim to address, remediate, accommodate, offset, or

reduce the likelihood of the onset or continuation of brain health issues, behavioral or cognitive deviations, or developmental concerns.

Comparison: As this is a scoping review aiming to map the breadth of community-based interventions in Africa, no specific comparison group (e.g., control or alternative intervention) is included. The focus is on describing the range of interventions and their characteristics without a baseline comparison.

Outcome: The review sought evidence on the outcomes and effectiveness of community-based programs and interventions in optimizing brain health, enhancing cognitive function, supporting neurodevelopment, or preventing cognitive decline across the lifespan. Outcomes are implicitly captured through the problem terms (e.g., "cognitive function," "brain health") and the impact of interventions on these areas.

Search Strategy

In the second stage of the review, all relevant studies were identified through a systematic search of online research databases, along with snowball sampling and reference tracking (i.e., examining reference lists of included sources and database alerts) to find additional articles. Database searches included PubMed, Scopus, ScienceDirect, and Web of Science. Key search terms, including synonyms and medical subject headings (MeSH terms), were systematically entered into these databases. The search included studies published from January 2020 to July 2025.

PubMed was searched first because it was deemed the most relevant for the study's goals. Terms were then adjusted as needed for each database search involved in the review.

Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria

For the third phase of the scoping review, data extracted from all databases were carefully aggregated and screened on their titles and abstracts while referencing the specified inclusion and exclusion criteria. Studies that were duplicated were dropped.

The following types of studies were included: studies that demonstrated a transparent, well-defined research methodology, including quantitative (such as randomized controlled trials, quasi-experimental designs, single-group pre-post studies with and without follow-up, case-control studies), qualitative (such as case studies, phenomenology, ethnography, grounded theory), or mixed methodologies. Studies that obtained data from a previous study to investigate associations between exposure and cognitive outcomes. These studies provided more evidence on community-based interventions, even though they did not implement a specific intervention technique.

The review excluded articles or studies that presented filtered information, such as systematic reviews, scoping reviews, evidence syntheses, narrative reviews, and qualitative syntheses. Qualitative analyses lacking rigorous qualitative methodologies were also excluded. Additionally, papers that offered clinical scenarios, vignettes, case descriptions, or clinical examples without reporting research methods consistent with qualitative case study approaches were not included.

Analysis approach

In the fourth stage of the review, the data was charted by developing an extraction tool, which was used alongside an Excel spreadsheet to systematically record relevant information from the included studies. The categories included in the data extraction tool and spreadsheet were as follows: (a) publication year, (b) author, (c) location of study (country), (d) life course stage targeted, (e) type of intervention, and (f) study outcomes.

Following the constraint of the personnel needed to review the extracted articles, the extraction was only performed by the author. The author used this tool to extract the data from each study independently included in this scoping review at regular intervals to ensure coding accuracy.

Figure 1: The PRISMA flow of the selection process

RESULTS

A total of 1603 studies were identified from the four databases: PubMed, Scopus, Science Direct and Web of Science. 977 studies were dropped because even though they looked at brain health factors, they were not carried out at the community level or involved any community-adapted strategy. 140 studies were dropped due to duplication. 211 studies were available for screening and reviewing to match the criteria. 32 studies were left for the final analysis; studies beyond intervention alone were included to increase the breadth of the review.

Studies were distributed across the continent, with South Africa contributing the most to this review (n = 10, 32%). Studies on physical health determinants had the highest entries (n = 19, 61%), followed by safety and security (n = 6, 19%). Environmental, access to services, learning and social connection determinants had two entries each.

The vast majority of studies (n = 10, 32%) adopted a longitudinal study, even though data from these studies were secondary analysis from the main study. Two significant studies provided data for secondary analysis, which were the Health and Ageing in Africa: A Longitudinal Study of an INDEPTH Community in South Africa (HAALSI) (Montana et al., 2021) and the Drakenstein Child Health Study (DCHS), also from South Africa (Donald et al., 2018).

Studies that primarily focused on children were (n = 12, 39%), while others collectively looked at mother and child. The majority of the adult-focused programs were in learning and social connection, safety and security, and environmental determinants.

The delivery method varied through the studies, with most being secondary analysis. Only two studies had an original intervention community program.

The information is captured in the following tables.

1. Physical Health Determinants

Author	Year	Country	Research/ Intervention design	Stage of life course	Research/ Intervention delivery
Naudé et al.	2022	South Africa	Cohort study	Children	African birth cohort study in a peri-urban area, engaging at the community level.
Mwakalebela et al.	2025	Tanzania	Cross-sectional study	Children	Utilized secondary data collected through the KaziAfya study from four public primary schools.
Shuffrey et al.	2022	South Africa	Prospective cohort study	Mother and Child	Utilized secondary data from the Safe Passage study.
Jensen et al.	2024	Tanzania	Psychosocial intervention	Children	Develop a psychosocial intervention for community management of SAM.
Parpia et al.	2021	Tanzania	Interventional trial	Children	Assessing the effect of antimicrobials and nicotinamide on linear growth in children.
Tomlinson et al.	2021	South Africa	Randomised controlled trial	Mother and Child	‘Thula Sana’ Programme for Mothers with Young Infants
Oyugi et al.	2025	Uganda	Cross-sectional study	Adults	Examined the association between hypertension and cognitive impairment in older persons in the community.
Chiwila et al.	2024	DR Congo, Zambia	Randomised clinical trial	Infants	Secondary analysis of a complementary feeding RCT.
Mwene-Batu et al.	2020	DR Congo	Cohort study	Adults	Explore the long-term effects of SAM during childhood on adults

						versus community controls.
Onyango et al.	2023	Kenya, Zambia	Cross-sectional study	Maternal and Child		Secondary data from a community-led parenting empowerment intervention.
Diarra et al.	2025	Mali	Cluster-randomised controlled trial	Children		Impact of micronutrient powders (MNP) on cognitive function in 60 communities.
Boivin et al.	2021	Benin	Cohort Study	Children		Rural administration of neurodevelopmental assessments in early childhood.
Nalwoga et al.	2025	Uganda	Cross-sectional study	Infants		Prevalence and factors associated with neurodevelopmental delay in preterm infants.
Ssemata et al.	2020	Uganda	Cohort study	Children		Effect of severe anaemia on neurodevelopment
Honja Kabero et al.	2021	Ethiopia	Cross-sectional study	Children		Neurodevelopmental tests and Mid-year average students' examination results were used to test for cognitive performance.
Ringshaw et al.	2025	South Africa	Sub-study	Children		Using neuroimaging to determine associations of antenatal maternal anaemia with child brain volumes.
Isong et al.	2024	Nigeria	Cross-sectional study	Adults		Households within communities were sampled and individuals had physical examinations and biomarker assessments associated with cognitive function.

Nwatah et al.	2022	Nigeria	Cross-sectional study	Adolescence	Using social demographic factors to determine cognitive function
Mutola et al.	2023	South Africa	Longitudinal Study	Adults	Used the multiple-mediation analysis on the HAALSI data to assess socioeconomic position and cognition.

2. Learning and Social Connection Determinants

Author	Year	Country	Research/ Intervention design	Stage of life course	Research/ Intervention delivery
Kyaw and Levine	2023	South Africa	Cross-sectional study	Adults	Cognitive performance was measured using a neuropsychological battery as the outcome.
Harling et al	2020	South Africa	Longitudinal study	Adults	Investigated patterns of social contact, social support and cognitive health

3. Safety and Security Determinants

Author	Year	Country	Research/ Intervention design	Stage of life course	Research/ Intervention delivery
Kobayashi et al	2020	South Africa	Longitudinal Study	Adults	Secondary data, Population-based survey
Nutakor et al	2021	Ghana	Longitudinal Study	Adults	Secondary data from SAGE study
Demis et al.	2022	Ethiopia	Longitudinal Study	Children	Secondary data from the

Author	Year	Country	Research/ Intervention design	Stage of life course	Research/ Intervention delivery
Kohler et al,	2023	Malawi	Longitudinal Study	Adults	Secondary data to predict levels of cognition
Jock et al.,	2024	South Africa	Quasi-experimental design	Adults	Pension association with Cognitive Function.
Payne et al.	2020	South Africa	Longitudinal Study	Adults	Secondary data to predict traumatic events with cognitive impairment.

*SAGE (“Study on Global AGEing and Adult Health (SAGE),” n.d.)

4. Environmental Determinants

Author	Year	Country	Research/ Intervention design	Stage of life course	Research/ Intervention delivery
Christensen et al.	2022	South Africa	Longitudinal Study	In-utero	Exposure was measured using devices placed in the families' homes
Kobayashi et al.	2022	South Africa	Longitudinal Study	Adults	Investigated relationships between long-term trends in household material resources and cognitive function.

5. Access to Services Determinants

Author	Year	Country	Research/ Intervention design	Stage of life course	Research/ Intervention delivery
Chin et al.	2025	Ethiopia	Longitudinal Study	Children	Experiences and lessons learned from implementing

					mobile EEG and VEP in rural Amhara
Wedderburn et al.	2020	South Africa	Cohort Study	Children	A sub-group of mother-child pairs were selected from the DCHS cohort for neuroimaging at 2–3 years of age.

Study Tools, Outcomes and Effectiveness

Only two studies adopted locally community interventions, 'Thula Sana', a home visiting intervention (Tomlinson et al., 2022) and a psychosocial stimulation intervention on children exposed to severe acute malnutrition (SAM) (Jensen et al., 2024). Studies employed various psychometric tools to assess cognitive outcomes. Some of the tools were adjusted to fit the local context. These included the Bayley Scales of Infant Development III Screening Test (BSID-III ST), which was adopted across several studies (Naudé et al., 2022; Shuffrey et al., 2022; Chiwila et al., 2024; Ssemata et al., 2020). Other tools used in the studies were Brief Infant-Toddler Social Emotional Assessment, Malawi Development Assessment Tool (MDAT), Mullen Scales of Early Learning (MSEL), Kaufman Assessment Battery for Children (KABC-II), the visual computerized Tests of Variables of Attention (TOVA), the Bruininks-Oseretsky Test (BOT-2) of motor proficiency, the Raven's Color Progressive Matrices (RCPM), Kaufman assessment battery for children (II), Raven's Standard Progressive Matrices (RSPM) and Ages and Stages Questionnaire – Third Edition (ASQ-3).

Primary outcomes were primarily cognitive functions and neurodevelopment. Of the 31 studies (n = 20, 66%), evidence of effectiveness or association between determinants and cognitive outcomes was shown.

6. Study Tools, Outcomes and Effectiveness

Reference	Investigation design/ tools	Primary Outcome	Secondary Outcome	Evidence of effectiveness
(Kobayashi et al., 2020)	The Oxford Cognitive Screen-Plus tool, designed for low-income settings.	Adverse childhood experiences and cognitive function		Childhood adversities are not associated with cognition.
(Naudé et al., 2022)	BSID-III	Maternal depressive symptoms	Children neurodevelopment	No significant association
(Mwakalebe la et al., 2025)	Actigraphy device, Flanker task, Tanita digital scale	Physical activity and cognitive performance	Nutritional status and cognitive performance.	No significant association
(Nutakor et al., 2021)	Secondary data from the SAGE study	Socioeconomic status and cognitive function		Yes. Higher education and higher income were significantly associated with better cognitive function.
(Kyaw and Levine, 2023)	Secondary data from the INDEPTH Study	Cognitive function	NA	Self-reported lower loneliness was associated with higher levels of cognitive performance.
(Shuffrey et al., 2022)	BSID-III ST	Maternal depression and adverse social-emotional outcomes	Cognitive scores	Yes. Maternal depression is associated with a reduction in cognitive scores.
(Demis et al., 2022)	Secondary data from Young Lives Study	Caregiver psychological distress, type of education	Cognitive development	Yes. Migration key determinant of childhood cognitive development.
(Kohler et al., 2023)	Secondary data from Mature Adults Cohort of the Malawi	Cognitive scores: language, attention, or		Women are particularly affected by poor

	Longitudinal Study of Families and Health.	executive of functioning.		cognition in this context
(Parpia et al., 2021)	The MDAT was used for children living in a rural sub-Saharan context.	Assess the impact of antimicrobials on child growth at 18 months of age.	Cognitive score at 18 months	No. The interventions had no effect on cognitive outcomes.
(Jensen et al., 2024)	Qualitative methods to inform the development of a psychosocial stimulation programme.	Develop a tool to promote cognitive development	NA	NA
(Jock et al., 2024)	Quasi-experimental design	Cognitive function		Yes. Potential benefit of cash transfers
(Tomlinson et al., 2022)	Thula Sana is a home-visiting intervention	child cognitive outcomes	maternal mood	No intervention effect on long-term child outcomes
(Oyugi et al., 2025)	community-based analysis, using MOCA	cognitive impairment		Yes. Hypertension was associated with cognitive impairment
(Chin et al., 2025)	Mobile EEG and Evoked Potential	Neurodevelopmental outcomes of children		Implementing mobile EEG/VEP was feasible and acceptable in rural Ethiopia
(Christensen et al., 2022)	Analysing prenatal exposure to air pollution	Increase in PM10. cognition, language, and adaptive behaviour sub-scores	Maternal smoking, lower adaptive behaviour scores.	Yes, association of PM10 and tobacco smoke on cognition, language, and adaptive behaviour.

(Chiwila et al., 2024)	BSID-III	Neurodevelopmental or growth outcomes.	NA	No association with junk food and neurodevelopmental conditions
(Payne et al., 2020)	Secondary data from the HAALSI Study	Later life mental outcomes	Physical and cognitive health outcomes	No. Trauma exposure was not associated with cognitive health.
(Mwene-Batu et al., 2020)	Cognition assessed with the MMSE	Education, cognition, self-esteem	Health-related disabilities in living	Mean scores in the cognitive test were lower in malnutrition survivors.
(Kobayashi et al., 2022)	Secondary data from the HAALSI Study	Cognitive function		Higher mean household resources were positively associated with cognitive function.
(Onyango et al., 2023)	The ASQ-3	Child development	NA	Positive link between maternal stimulation activities and children's developmental
(Diarra et al., 2025)	Impact of micronutrient powders (MNP)	Anemia	Stunting and cognitive function	No effect was observed on stunting or cognitive function.
(Boivin et al., 2021)	KABC-II, TOVA and the BOT-2 of motor proficiency	Neurodevelopmental assessments in early childhood		Neurodevelopmental assessments are predictive of school-age neuropsychological cognitive ability.
(Nalwoga et al., 2025)	NA Prevalence study	- Factors associated with		Microcephaly, SAM, incomplete immunization,

			neurodevelopmental delay			neonatal sepsis, neonatal hypoglycemia, lack of caretaker social support and large family size.
(Ssemata et al., 2020)	BSID-III		Neurodevelopmental performance of preschool children			In children < 5 years of age, severe anaemia was associated with neurocognitive deficits.
(Wedderburn et al., 2020)	MRI		Feasibility of paediatric multimodal MRI			Dynamic morphological changes in heteromodal association regions are associated with cognitive and language development.
(Honja Kabero et al., 2021)	RCPM and KABC		Cognitive function.	School performance		Cognitive function and school performance are associated with nutritional status.
(Ringshaw et al., 2025)	Neuroimaging sub-study (From DCHS)		Maternal and child anemia	Child brain volumes		No change in brain volumes attributed to maternal anemia.
(Isong et al., 2024)	Prevalence of Metabolic syndrome and Cognitive impairment among older adults		cognitive status			MetS as a whole is not associated with CI, but reduced HDL levels are significantly linked to poor cognitive status.

(Harling et al., 2020)	Secondary data from the HAALSI Study.	Cognitive decline	Lower cognitive function was associated with receipt of less social support.
(Nwatah et al., 2022)	RSPM	Cognitive function	Predictors of IQ performance were the student's age, maternal age and school type.
(Mutola et al., 2023)	Secondary data from the HAALSI Study	Cognitive function	Low socioeconomic position is a significant factor associated with poor cognitive function among adults.

DISCUSSION

This review examined community-based interventions and programs addressing determinants of brain health across Africa over the past five years. Only two studies, ‘Thula Sana’: a home visiting intervention and another study on psychosocial stimulation intervention, reported the development of community-led interventions, highlighting a substantial gap in initiatives explicitly designed to mitigate brain health risks across the life course at the community level (Tomlinson et al., 2022; Jensen et al., 2024).. Nonetheless, several community-based programs provided valuable insights and established a foundation for future research and intervention development. Two longitudinal studies, the HAALSI, a population ageing study, and DCHS, an early child development and cognition study, provided data that allowed various investigators to assess the interplay of brain health determinants and cognitive outcomes in these populations (Montana et al., 2021; Donald et al., 2018).

Most studies explored physical health determinants and their associations with brain health, typically assessed through cognitive function outcomes. Evidence of effectiveness was generally inferred through the linkage of specific physical domains, such as adequate nutrition, physical activity or maternal and health outcomes to cognitive performance. These translated to a considerable proportion of interventions focusing on children and neurodevelopment, with maternal and child health emerging as a recurring theme. These studies underscored the critical role of maternal health in shaping early brain outcomes, consistent with evidence that postpartum health is closely tied to infant neurodevelopment and influenced by the same social determinants of health (SDOH). Disparities in breastfeeding intent and completion, shaped by education, employment, food security, neighbourhood resources, and housing, were particularly noted. The strong focus on children and mothers reflects the demographic structure of Africa, where a predominantly young population makes early-life interventions particularly relevant.

Among adult populations, studies frequently relied on secondary data to examine financial and social determinants of brain health. Security and income stability emerged as central themes, with a specific emphasis on the role of pensions in protecting late-life cognitive health (Mostert et al., 2025b). Strengthening pension systems may therefore represent a critical policy pathway for safeguarding brain health across the region.

Finally, the tools used to assess cognitive outcomes were primarily drawn from standardised international measures. The adoption of such tools is crucial for ensuring comparability, replicability, and validation of brain health research across diverse African contexts.

Limitations

As a scoping review aimed at understanding the current state of Africa community-based interventions and programs related to the WHO brain health determinants, the review excluded any literature published before 2020 and papers from outside Africa. This meant that earlier work and studies from other countries were overlooked, which could be relevant to the current African context. While care was taken to ensure the search strategy was as inclusive as possible within the set parameters, conducting the review as a single individual increases the chance of missing some literature due to indexing or other reasons. Additional interventions and insights may also be found in grey literature.

CONCLUSION

This scoping review highlights both the promise and the gaps in community-based approaches to brain health across Africa. While a few notable interventions, such as maternal home visiting and psychosocial stimulation programs, demonstrate the feasibility and potential of community-led strategies, the overall evidence base remains limited. The majority of studies focused on maternal and child health, reflecting Africa's young

demographic profile, with relatively fewer interventions addressing brain health in adulthood and older age.

The findings underscore the importance of embedding brain health promotion within the broader framework of social determinants of health and aligning interventions with the WHO's five determinant clusters. Efforts around nutrition, maternal health, social protection, and pension systems show potential pathways for strengthening cognitive outcomes across the life course. However, the scarcity of rigorously designed, locally led, and context-sensitive interventions highlights a pressing need for greater investment in African-led brain health research and practice.

Future work should focus on developing and assessing scalable, community-led frameworks that address Africa's unique demographic, social, and economic contexts. When systematically advanced, such approaches have the potential to decrease the increasing burden of brain health conditions, promote equality, and improve cognitive resilience across generations.

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